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New Ideas In Cancer's Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission

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1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Clique-Decompositions pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a, E'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a, E'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a, V'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a, V'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. ((Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive

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 corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is 113
 introduced for new SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions 114
 and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Two different types of 115
 SuperHyperDefinitions are debut for them but the research goes further and the 116
 SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass based on that are 117
 well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature review is implemented in the whole of 118
 this research. For shining the elegancy and the significancy of this research, the 119
 comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and 120
 fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions are followed by the 121
 examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with different tools. The 122
 applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical aspect of this ongoing 123
 research. The "Cancer's Recognition" are the under research to figure out the 124
 challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special case is up. 125
 The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them. Some of 126
 them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells. These 127
 types are all officially called "SuperHyperVertex" but the relations amid them all 128
 officially called "SuperHyperEdge". The frameworks "SuperHyperGraph" and 129
 "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" are chosen and elected to research about "Cancer's 130
 Recognition". Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues 131
 to research on theoretical segments and "Cancer's Recognition". Some avenues are 132
 posed to pursue this research. It's also officially collected in the form of some questions 133
 and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then 134
 δ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a 135
 maximum cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the 136
 (Neutrosophic) cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are 137
 $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first 138
 Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds 139
 if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic 140
 δ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is a maximal Neutrosophic of 141
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following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are: $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$; 143
 and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression, 144
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 type-results to make a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions more understandable. For 148
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 "The Values of The Vertices & The Number of Position in Alphabet", "The Values of 157
 The SuperVertices&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The 158
 Edges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The HyperEdges&The 159
 maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The 160
 maximum Values of Its Endpoints". To get structural examples and instances, I'm 161
 going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of SuperHyperGraph based on a 162
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 and a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and 173
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 a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's redefined "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" if 176
 the intended Table holds. And a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions are redefined to a 177
 "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" if the intended Table holds. It's 178
 useful to define "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways 179
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 SuperHyperClique-Decompositions more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic 181
 SuperHyperGraph. There are some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended 182
 Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, 183
 SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and 184
 SuperHyperWheel, are "Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath", "Neutrosophic 185
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 maximum value amid all SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions 191
 .] SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it's a 192
 SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. 193
 Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as 194
 195

follows. It's SuperHyperPath if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it's SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperStar it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperBipartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's SuperHyperMultiPartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multiple separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's a SuperHyperWheel if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". In this SuperHyperModel, The "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperVertices" and the common and intended properties between "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperEdges". Sometimes, it's useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called "Neutrosophic". In the future research, the foundation will be based on the "Cancer's Recognition" and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions or the strongest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, called SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and the strongest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. There isn't any formation of any SuperHyperClique-Decompositions but literarily, it's the deformation of any SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer's attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer's attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as "new groups". Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I've found the SuperHyperModels which are officially called "SuperHyperGraphs" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperVertices" and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperEdges". Thus it's another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the "Cancer's Recognition". Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it's the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperGraph but it's officially called "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what's going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the "Cancer's Recognition" and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances' styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called "SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix "SuperHyper" refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperClique-Decompositions or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a

SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. There isn't any formation of any
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions but literarily, it's the deformation of any
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the "amount of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the "amount of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the "Cancer's Recognition" in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It's motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled "SuperHyperGraphs". Thus it motivates us to define different types of "SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" on "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, "Cancer's Recognition", more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection "Preliminaries", initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what's going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, are figured out in sections "SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions". In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Clique-Decompositions to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what's done in this section, titled "Results on SuperHyperClasses" and "Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses". As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in the sections "Results on SuperHyperClasses" and "Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses". The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section "General Results". Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, "General Results", "SuperHyperClique-Decompositions", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions", "Results on SuperHyperClasses" and "Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses". There are curious questions about what's done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word "best" as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, "SuperHyperClique-Decompositions". The keyword of this research debut in the section "Applications in Cancer's Recognition" with two cases and subsections "Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as

SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel”. In the section, “Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what’s done and what’s happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [120]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [120]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Clique-Decompositions of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.2,p.2).

Let X be a Clique-Decompositions of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\begin{aligned} T_A(X) &= \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}, \\ I_A(X) &= \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}, \\ \text{and } F_A(X) &= \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;

- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 403
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 404
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 405
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- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 407
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- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 409
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If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 411
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Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3). 413

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$: 414
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- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$; 416
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$; 417
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$; 418
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$. 419

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). 420

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where 421
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- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ; 423
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 424
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- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ; 426
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- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 428
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- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 430
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 431

$$(vii) \sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V, (i = 1, 2, \dots, n);$$

$$(viii) \sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V, (i' = 1, 2, \dots, n').$$

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;

- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$.

Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**;
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**;
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**;
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**.

Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). (Ref. [120], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$.

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [120], Definition 5.4, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a, E'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a, E'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

$$\text{and } |E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a, V'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a, V'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique-Decompositions).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme

SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;
- (v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

(i) an δ -**SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)| &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)| &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

(ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions such that either of the following Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive**.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath , SuperHyperClique-Decompositions,

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite**, and **Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions more Neutrosophicly understandable. For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the Table (3) holds.

4 Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 4.1. (Neutrosophic event).

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Any Neutrosophic k -subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Neutrosophic subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic event**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 4.2. (Neutrosophic Independent).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. s Neutrosophic k -events A_i , $i \in I$ is called **Neutrosophic s -independent** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic s -independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Neutrosophic k -events of A and B is called **Neutrosophic independent**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Neutrosophic Variable).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Any k -function Clique-Decompositions like E is called **Neutrosophic k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Clique-Decompositions like E is called **Neutrosophic Variable**.

The notion of independent on Neutrosophic Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Neutrosophic Expectation).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Expectation** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Neutrosophic Crossing).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A Neutrosophic number is called **Neutrosophic Crossing** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Crossing criteria**

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let m and n propose special Clique-Decompositions. Then with $m \geq 4n$,

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be a Neutrosophic random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Neutrosophic independently with probability Clique-Decompositions $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$.

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Neutrosophic number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Zcr(H)Y - 3X$. By linearity of Neutrosophic Expectation,

$$E(Z)E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pn$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G)p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have:

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

□ 730

Theorem 4.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

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Proof. Form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between consecutive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$. □

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Theorem 4.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$.

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Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Draw a SuperHyperUnit SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Neutrosophic number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between consecutive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

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$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with $e(G)k - n$. Now $cr(G)n(n-1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n-1)cr(G)(k-n)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$. □

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Proposition 4.9. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X be a nonnegative Neutrosophic Variable and t a positive real number. Then

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Clique-Decompositions $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof.

Theorem 4.11. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k+1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Neutrosophic Variable for this Neutrosophic Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k+1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k+1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k+1\} = \binom{n}{k+1} (1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$\binom{n}{k+1} \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1 - p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$.

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p \binom{k+1}{2}}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{n e^{-pk/2k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k2p^{-1} \log n$, so $ne^{-pk/2} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . $\square$

Definition 4.12. (Neutrosophic Variance).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Variance** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Variance criteria**

$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Corollary 4.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X_n be a Neutrosophic Variable in a probability Clique-Decompositions (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then

$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$ in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$ when $X_n = 0$. $\square$

Theorem 4.15. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k)2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. As in the proof of related Theorem, the result is straightforward. $\square$

Corollary 4.16. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either:

(i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$,
or

(ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* .

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$.
Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. The latter is
straightforward. $\square$

Definition 4.17. (Neutrosophic Threshold).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider
 $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let P be a monotone property of
SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a
Neutrosophic Threshold for P is a function $f(n)$ such that:

(i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P ,

(ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P .

Definition 4.18. (Neutrosophic Balanced).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider
 $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let F be a fixed Neutrosophic
SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a
copy of F as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Neutrosophic Balanced**.

Theorem 4.19. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let F be a
nonempty balanced Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l
SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F
as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$.
Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. The latter is
straightforward. $\square$

Example 4.20. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is
Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic
SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic
SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that
there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} = \{\{E_4\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_1\}, \{V_2\}, \{V_3\}, \{V_1, V_2\}, \{V_1, V_4\}, \{V_2, V_4\}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 3}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_4\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_1\}, \{V_2\}, \{V_3\}, \{V_1, V_2\}, \{V_1, V_4\}, \{V_2, V_4\}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_4\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_1\}, \{V_2\}, \{V_3\}, \{V_1, V_2\}, \{V_1, V_4\}, \{V_2, V_4\}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 4. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_4\}, \{E_5\}, \{E_1, E_4\}, \{E_1, E_5\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_2, V_3, N, F, V_4\}, \{V_1, V_2, V_3, N, F, H\}, \{V_1, V_2, V_3, N, F, O\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 3z^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}_{i \neq j}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{Four Choose Two})z^2. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{i=1}^5, \{V_i\}_{i=5}^8, \dots\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^5 + 2z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

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Figure 5. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophicly straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{E_1, E_2\}, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= bz. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} = \\ & \{\{E_i, E_{13}, E_{14}, E_{16}\}_{i=3}^7, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^8 + z^7. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} = \\ & \{\{V_i, V_{13}\}_{i=4}^7, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^5 + z^4. \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 6. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 7. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 8. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
 \{E_i\}_{i=1}^4 & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 z^4 & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
 \{\{V_{13}, V_i\}_{i=4}^7, \{V_{14}, V_i\}_{i=8}^{11}, \{V_{12}, V_i\}_{i=1}^3, \{V_i\}_{i=12}^{14}\} & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 2z^5 + z^4 + z^3 &
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
 \{\{E_i, E_{i+1}\}_{i=1}^{10}\} & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 az^2 & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
 \{\{V_i, V_{i+1}\}_{i=1}^{10}, \{V_i, V_{22}\}_{i=11}^{20}\} & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 az^2 + z^{11} &
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 9. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{E_1, E_4, E_5, E_6, \{E_4, E_5, E_6\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^1 + z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_{13}, V_i\}_{i=4}^7, \{V_{14}, V_i\}_{i=8}^{11}, \{V_{12}, V_i\}_{i=1}^3, \{V_i\}_{i=12}^{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^5 + z^4 + z^3. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}, \{E_2, E_4, E_5\}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4 + z^3 + az^2 + 7z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_4, V_5, V_6\}, \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^3 + az^2 + 6z. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 10. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{E_1, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= az^2 + 6z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_7, V_8\}, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5 + az^2 + 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}, \{E_2, E_4, E_5\}, \{E_1, E_9, E_{10}\}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4 + 2z^3 + az^2 + 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_4, V_5, V_6\}, \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^3 + az^2 + 6z. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 11. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 12. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 13. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= az^2 + 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2 + 3z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2 + 5z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2 + 6z. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 14. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 16. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 4z^2 + 5z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{17}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{10} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 4z^2 + 5z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{17}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{10} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 17. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 4z^2 + 5z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{17}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{10} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^2 + 12z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_8}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^9 + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 18. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = az^2 + 10z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_6}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = az^b + \dots + kz. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

Figure 19. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 20. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 21. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^2 + 2z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_2}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{10} + \dots + 10z. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

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Figure 22. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{E_1, E_2, E_3\}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^3 + az^2 + 5z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_3}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{12} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

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Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

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Proposition 4.22. Assume a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

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Proposition 4.23. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions.

Proposition 4.24. Assume a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the Neutrosophic number of type-result-R-Clique-Decompositions has, the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for Neutrosophic cardinality, is the Neutrosophic cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

If there's a Neutrosophic type-result-R-Clique-Decompositions with the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for cardinality.

Proposition 4.25. Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Is a Neutrosophic type-result-Clique-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic type-result-Clique-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The SuperHyperSet of the SuperHyperVertices $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions since neither amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges nor amount of SuperHyperVertices where amount refers to the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices(-/SuperHyperEdges) more than one to form any kind of SuperHyperEdges or any number of SuperHyperEdges. Let us consider the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality indicates that these Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Neutrosophic lower bound in the term of Neutrosophic sharpness. In other words, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Neutrosophic structure of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions decorates the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Neutrosophic connections so as this Neutrosophic style implies different versions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Neutrosophic bound is to have the maximum Neutrosophic groups of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have

perfect Neutrosophic connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph arising from its Neutrosophic properties taken from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, then there's no Neutrosophic connection. Furthermore, the Neutrosophic existence of one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no Neutrosophic effect to talk about the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. Since at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Neutrosophic background of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge but at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices make the Neutrosophic version of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Neutrosophic setting of non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Neutrosophic adjective for the initial Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Neutrosophic appearance of the loop Neutrosophic version of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and this Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Neutrosophic adjective "loop" on the basic Neutrosophic framework engages one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Neutrosophic setting. With these Neutrosophic bases, on a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions has the Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus, a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions has the Neutrosophic cardinality at least a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet isn't a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions since either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since there's no Neutrosophic usage of this Neutrosophic framework and even more there's no Neutrosophic connection inside or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph isn't obvious and as its consequences, there's a Neutrosophic contradiction with the term "Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions" since the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality never happens for this Neutrosophic style of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Neutrosophic connection inside as mentioned in first Neutrosophic case in the forms of drawback for this selected Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Comes up. This Neutrosophic case implies having the Neutrosophic style of on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style on the every Neutrosophic elements of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that some Neutrosophic amount of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style. The Neutrosophic cardinality of the v SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}.$$

But the lower Neutrosophic bound is up. Thus the minimum Neutrosophic cardinality of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality ends up the Neutrosophic discussion. The first Neutrosophic term refers to the Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic

SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClass of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style amid some amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. This Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel proposes a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has only some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Neutrosophic amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The Neutrosophic cardinality of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Neutrosophic case is occurred in the minimum Neutrosophic situation. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Has the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Contains some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices taken from the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

It means that the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as used Neutrosophic background in the Neutrosophic terms of worst Neutrosophic case and the common theme of the lower Neutrosophic bound occurred in the specific Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are Neutrosophic free-quasi-triangle. 993
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Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Then every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has at least no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with others in common. Thus those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be contained in a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. Those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are potentially included in a Neutrosophic style-R-Clique-Decompositions. Formally, consider

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The formal definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and there's only and only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Neutrosophic

SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions but with slightly differences in the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality amid those Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z |\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}|_{\text{Neutrosophic cardinality}},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Neutrosophic

R-Clique-Decompositions. Let $Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

But with the slightly differences,

Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions =

$$\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \stackrel{E_x}{\sim} Z_j\}.$$

Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions =

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. for all Neutrosophic intended SuperHyperVertices but in a Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions.

The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel addresses some issues about the Neutrosophic optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is either has the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions where the Neutrosophic completion of the Neutrosophic incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literarily, a Neutrosophic embedded R-Clique-Decompositions. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those SuperHyperSets have the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality and they're Neutrosophic SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Neutrosophic style of the embedded Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. The interior types of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices pose the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. Thus Neutrosophic exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and in Neutrosophic SuperHyperRelation with the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions, there's the usage of exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the title "exterior" is more relevant than the title "interior". One Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. The Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and with other terms, the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions with the inclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

The main definition of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions has two titles. a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions and its corresponded quasi-maximum Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For any Neutrosophic number, there's a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions with that quasi-maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the

embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If there's an embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, then the Neutrosophic quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositionss for all Neutrosophic numbers less than its Neutrosophic corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositionss acted on the all possible used formations of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Neutrosophic number. This Neutrosophic number is

considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Clique-Decompositionss. Let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}}$ be a Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and a Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} &= G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}}, \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions is re-formalized and redefined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} &= G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}}, \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal technical definition for the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} &= G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}}, \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\ = z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\ = \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. & \end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions poses the upcoming expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\ = \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. & \end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised. 1082

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

And then, 1083

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook. 1084

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\
S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}}, \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

1085

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\
S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}}, \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

1086

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

1087

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood”, could be redefined as the collection of the 1088
1089

Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are incident to a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It's, literarily, another name for "Neutrosophic Quasi-Clique-Decompositions" but, precisely, it's the generalization of "Neutrosophic Quasi-Clique-Decompositions" since "Neutrosophic Quasi-Clique-Decompositions" happens "Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions" in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but "Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood" may not happens "Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions" in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality arise from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, "Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood", "Neutrosophic Quasi-Clique-Decompositions", and "Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions" are up.

Thus, let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}}$ be a Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood and a Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions and the new terms are up.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure,

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$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

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To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

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The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is an **Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge amid some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions** is related to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

There's not only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

doesn't have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet since they've come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Clique-Decompositions**. Since it's **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions. There isn't only less than two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the

Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions,

is only and only

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only a Neutrosophic free-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel and a Neutrosophic on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also it's a Neutrosophic stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions amid those obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$.

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHypeNeighbors to any amount of them.

Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices r . Consider all Neutrosophic numbers of those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge excluding more than r distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions with the least cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for Neutrosophic cardinality. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. Since it doesn't have

the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but it isn't a Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions. Since it **doesn't do** the Neutrosophic procedure such that such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely [there are at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, sometimes in the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, titled its Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the Neutrosophic procedure"]. There's only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **outside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions, V_{ESHE} is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions, V_{ESHE} , **is** a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only **all** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Neutrosophic pairs are titled Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices V_{ESHE} , is the

maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely. Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any Neutrosophic R-Clique-Decompositions only contains all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and all exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from the unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge where there's any of them has all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods in with no exception minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods and Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors out.

The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Clique-Decompositions, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions. The

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1184

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic 1185
Clique-Decompositions. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic 1186
SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1187

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an **Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic 1188
SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with 1189
the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of 1190
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic 1191
SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an 1192
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There are not 1193
only **two** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic 1194
SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions is up. The 1195
obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic 1196
Clique-Decompositions is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two** 1197
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the 1198
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1199

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic 1200
SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the 1201
Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic 1202

SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Clique-Decompositions**. Since it's **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions, 1219

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic 1220
Clique-Decompositions, not: 1221

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not: 1222

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic 1223
SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious 1224
simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the 1225

“Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions” 1226

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the 1227

Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions, 1228

is only and only 1229

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. □ 1230

5 The Neutrosophic Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses.

Proposition 5.1. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (|E_{NSHG}| - 1)z^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{\max |E_b|_{E_b \in E_{NSHG}}} + \dots + az.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Example (16.5)

Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$.
Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (|E_{NSHG}|)z^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{\max |E_b|_{E_b \in E_{NSHG}}} + \dots + az.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.9)

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_1, E_2\}_{i=1}^{|P_{NSHG}^{\max}|}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= az^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P_i \in \{P_a \mid |P_a| = \max |P_b|_{P_b \in P_{NSHG}}\}}, \{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{\max |P_b|_{P_b \in P_{NSHG}}} + z^{\max |E_b|_{E_b \in E_{NSHG}}} + \dots + az.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{|P_i| = \min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{|P_i| = \min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{|P_i| = \min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i| = \min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperClique-Decompositions could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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Figure 26. Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Example (16.11)

minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 5.8. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

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Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{ \{E_1, E_2\}_{i=1}^{|P_{NSHG}^{\max}|}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\} \}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{ \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P_i \in \{P_a \mid |P_a| = \max |P_b|_{P_b \in P_{NSHG}}\}}, \{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V \} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\max |P_b|_{P_b \in P_{NSHG}}} + z^{\max |E_b|_{E_b \in E_{NSHG}}} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperClique-Decompositions could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.15)

The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperClique-Decompositions could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperClique-Decompositions proposes some longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.12. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

6 The Surveys of Mathematical Sets On The Results But As The Initial Motivation

For the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, some general results are introduced.

Remark 6.1. Let remind that the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is “redefined” on the positions of the alphabets.

Corollary 6.2. Assume Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique – Decompositions} = \\
 & \{ \text{the SuperHyperClique – Decompositions of the SuperHyperVertices} | \\
 & \max | \text{SuperHyperOffensive} \\
 & \text{SuperHyperClique – Decompositions} \\
 & | \text{Neutrosophic cardinality among those SuperHyperClique – Decompositions.} \}
 \end{aligned}$$

plus one Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to one. Where σ_i is the unary operation on the SuperHyperVertices of the SuperHyperGraph to assign the determinacy, the indeterminacy and the neutrality, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively.

Corollary 6.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then the notion of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and SuperHyperClique-Decompositions coincide. 1355
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Corollary 6.4. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a consecutive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if and only if it's a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1358
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Corollary 6.5. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a consecutive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a strongest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if and only if it's a longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1362
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Corollary 6.6. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and reversely. 1366
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Corollary 6.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel) on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and reversely. 1369
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Corollary 6.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions isn't well-defined. 1374
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Corollary 6.9. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions isn't well-defined. 1377
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Corollary 6.10. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions isn't well-defined. 1380
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Corollary 6.11. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is well-defined. 1385
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Corollary 6.12. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is well-defined. 1388
1389
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Corollary 6.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is well-defined. 1391
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Proposition 6.14. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then V is 1396
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(i) : the dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1398

(ii) : the strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1399

(iii) : the connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1400

(iv) : the δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1401

(v) : the strong δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1402

(vi) : the connected δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1403

Proposition 6.15. Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then $\emptyset$ is 1404

(i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1406

(ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1407

(iii) : the connected defensive SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1408

(iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1409

(v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1410

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1411

Proposition 6.16. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then an independent SuperHyperSet is 1412

(i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1414

(ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1415

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1416

(iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1417

(v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1418

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1419

Proposition 6.17. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal 1420

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1423

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1424

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1425

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1426

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1427

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1428

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1429

Proposition 6.18. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal 1430

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1432

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1433

(iii) : *connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1434

(iv) : *$\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1435

(v) : *strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1436

(vi) : *connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1437
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Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1439

Proposition 6.19. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of* 1440
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(i) : *the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1443

(ii) : *the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1444

(iii) : *the connected SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1445

(iv) : *the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1446

(v) : *the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1447

(vi) : *the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1448

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1449
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Proposition 6.20. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of* 1451
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(i) : *the dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1453

(ii) : *the dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1454

(iii) : *the dual connected SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1455

(iv) : *the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1456

(v) : *the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1457

(vi) : *the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1458

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1459
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Proposition 6.21. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a* 1461
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(i) : *dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1466

(ii) : *strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1467

(iii) : *connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1468

(iv) : *$\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1469

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1470

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1471
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Proposition 6.22. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a 1473
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1479

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1480

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1481

(iv) : δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1482

(v) : strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1483

(vi) : connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1484

Proposition 6.23. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then Then the number of 1485
1486
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(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1489

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1490

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1491

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1492

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1493

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1494
1495

is one and it's only S , a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1496
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Proposition 6.24. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual 1500
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1502

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1503

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1504

(iv) : SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1505

(v) : strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1506

(vi) : *connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1507

Proposition 6.25. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Neutrosophic number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$.* 1508
1509

Proposition 6.26. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual* 1510
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1512

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1513

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1514

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1515

(iv) : *($\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1516

(v) : *strong ($\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1517
1518

(vi) : *connected ($\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1519
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Proposition 6.27. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$. The number is 0 and the Neutrosophic number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual* 1521
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1524

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1525

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1526

(iv) : *0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1527

(v) : *strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1528

(vi) : *connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1529

Proposition 6.28. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet.* 1530
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Proposition 6.29. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperClique-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual* 1532
1533
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1536

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1537

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1538

(iv) : *$\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1539

(v) : *strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1540
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(vi) : *connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1542
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Proposition 6.30. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1548
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1549
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1550
- (iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1551
- (v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1552
1553
- (vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1554
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Proposition 6.31. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the $ESHGs : (V, E)$ Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. 1556
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Proposition 6.32. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that 1561
1562
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- (i) $v \in N_s(x)$; 1564
- (ii) $vx \in E$. 1565

Proposition 6.33. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then 1566
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- (i) S is SuperHyperClique-Decompositions set; 1568
- (ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number. 1569

Proposition 6.34. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then 1570
1571

- (i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$; 1572
- (ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$. 1573

Proposition 6.35. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then 1574
1575

- (i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$; 1576
- (ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$. 1577

Proposition 6.36. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then 1578

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1579
1580
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1581

- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\};$ 1582
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1583
1584

Proposition 6.37. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an even SuperHyperPath. Then* 1585

- (i) *the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1586
1587
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ *and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;* 1588
1589
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\};$ 1590
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1591
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Proposition 6.38. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an even SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Then* 1593
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- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1595
1596
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ *and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;* 1597
1598
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\};$ 1599
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1600
1601

Proposition 6.39. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an odd SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Then* 1602
1603

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1604
1605
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ *and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;* 1606
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\};$ 1607
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1608
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Proposition 6.40. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be SuperHyperStar. Then* 1610

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1611
- (ii) $\Gamma = 1;$ 1612
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c);$ 1613
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1614
1615

Proposition 6.41. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be SuperHyperWheel. Then* 1616

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1617
1618

$$(ii) \Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \cdots, v_{i+6}, \cdots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|; \quad 1619$$

$$(iii) \Gamma_s = \Sigma_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \cdots, v_{i+6}, \cdots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s); \quad 1620$$

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \cdots, v_{i+6}, \cdots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1621
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Proposition 6.42. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then 1623

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1624
1625

$$(ii) \Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1; \quad 1626$$

$$(iii) \Gamma_s = \min\{\Sigma_{s \in S} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}; \quad 1627$$

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1628
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Proposition 6.43. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then 1630

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1631
1632

$$(ii) \Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor; \quad 1633$$

$$(iii) \Gamma_s = \min\{\Sigma_{s \in S} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}; \quad 1634$$

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1635
1636

Proposition 6.44. Let $NSHF : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStars with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1637
1638

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \cdots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $NSHF$; 1639
1640

$$(ii) \Gamma = m \text{ for } NSHF : (V, E); \quad 1641$$

$$(iii) \Gamma_s = \Sigma_{i=1}^m \Sigma_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i) \text{ for } NSHF : (V, E); \quad 1642$$

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \cdots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $NSHF : (V, E)$. 1643
1644

Proposition 6.45. Let $NSHF : (V, E)$ be an m -SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1645
1646
1647

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $NSHF$; 1648
1649

$$(ii) \Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1 \text{ for } NSHF : (V, E); \quad 1650$$

$$(iii) \Gamma_s = \min\{\Sigma_{s \in S} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}} \text{ for } NSHF : (V, E); \quad 1651$$

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $NSHF : (V, E)$. 1652
1653

Proposition 6.46. *Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then*

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$;*
- (ii) *$\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$;*
- (iii) *$\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$;*
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$.*

Proposition 6.47. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;*
- (ii) *if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.*

Proposition 6.48. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;*
- (ii) *if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.*

Proposition 6.49. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;*
- (ii) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;*
- (iii) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;*
- (iv) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.*

Proposition 6.50. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *$\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;*

(ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1695
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(iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1697
1698

(iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual
 V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1699
1700

Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an]
[V -]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a
SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1701
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(i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1704
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(ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1706
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(iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1708
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(iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual
 $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1710
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Proposition 6.52. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an]
[V -]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a
SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1712
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(i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1715
1716

(ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1717
1718

(iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is
 $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1719
1720

(iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual
 $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1721
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Proposition 6.53. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an]
[V -]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Then following statements hold; 1723
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1725

(i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1726
1727

(ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1728
1729

(iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1730
1731

(iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1732
1733

Proposition 6.54. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an]
[V -]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Then following statements hold; 1734
1735
1736

- (i) if $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1737
1738
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1739
1740
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1741
1742
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1743
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7 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease. 1747
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In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease. 1753

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function. 1754
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Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. 1756
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Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. 1764
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8 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. 1776
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Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

By using the Neutrosophic Figure (29) and the Table (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained.

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (29), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

9 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.

By using the Neutrosophic Figure (30) and the Table (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained.

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (30), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?*

Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions?*

Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions?*

Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, are there else?*

Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 10.7. *What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted.

This research uses some approaches to make Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new definition for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it’s mentioned on the title “Cancer’s Recognitions”. To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, the new SuperHyperClasses and SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognitions” and both bases are the background of this research.

Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called “ SuperHyperClique-Decompositions” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table (6), benefits and avenues for this

Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperClique-Decompositions	
3. Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer’s Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out.

12 Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{NSHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{NSHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{NSHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{NSHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality.

Definition 12.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;

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- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality;

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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;

1910
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1917
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic

1918
1919
1920
1921
1922

SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality;

- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 12.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Neutrosophic

SuperHyperDuality. 1966

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1967
1968
1969

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1970
1971
1972

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1973
1974
1975

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1976
1977
1978

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1979
1980
1981

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1982
1983
1984

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1985
1986
1987

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1988
1989
1990

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1991
1992
1993

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1994
1995
1996

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1997
1998
1999

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2000
2001
2002

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2003
2004
2005

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2006
2007
2008

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2009
2010
2011

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2012
2013
2014

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (2 \times 2 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2015
2016
2017

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0}^5}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2018
2019
2020

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2021
2022
2023

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2024
2025
2026

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2027
2028

Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then*

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}, \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any

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solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □ 2080

Example 12.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality. 2081
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Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then 2087
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic \text{ Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2089

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2090
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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is 2092
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straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied.
 There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one
 SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only
 minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any
 solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.
 The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic
 result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27),
 is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i | E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}^*, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z^* &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z^*. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

13 Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin.

Definition 13.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;

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- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin;

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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic

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SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin;

- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 13.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus

the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin. 2243
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2245
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2248
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2251
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2254
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2257
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2260
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2263
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2266
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2269
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2272
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2275
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2278
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2281
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2284
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2287
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2290
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2293
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2296
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2299
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2302
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2305
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Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &\underline{E}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, \underline{V}^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.10. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite ESHB : (V, E). Then*

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite ESHB : (V, E). There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied.

There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \prod |V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

14 Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect;

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- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect;

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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic

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SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect;

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 14.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus

the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect. 2521
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2523
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2526
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2529
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2532
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2535
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2538
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2541
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2544
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2547
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 3 \times 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2550
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5, 7, 8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2553
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2556
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2559
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2562
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2565
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2568
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2571
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=03}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=05}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2574
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2577
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2580
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2583
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Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

{},

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)$$

$$z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}|$$

$$= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$P :$

$V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1,$

$V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2,$

$\dots,$

$E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be

applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 14.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;
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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
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- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a
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Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2804
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2807
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2810
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2813
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2816
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly 2819
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2837
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2840
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2843
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2846
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2849
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2852
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2855
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2858
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2861
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Proposition 15.4. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then* 2863
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2865

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3, \\ \dots \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath
 $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &\quad \cdot |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2} \cdot |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ \frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1}}{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is
straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite
 $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ &\forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 15.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}|$$

$$= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}}$$

$$= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{EXTERNAL}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{EXTERNAL}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

16 Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected** if
 $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$

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- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected** if
 $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$ and
 $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$

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- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected** if
 $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$

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- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected** if
 $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a;$ $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and
 $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$

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- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected.

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Definition 16.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

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- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected;

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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected;

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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

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Example 16.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3091
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3094
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3097
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3100
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3103
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^{19}, V_{22}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 3106
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3124
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3127
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3130
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3133
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3136
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3139
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3142
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 3145
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Proposition 16.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 3147
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 3149

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}^{EXTERNAL}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 3150
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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1) \\ & \quad z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.

Then

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}^z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

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Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| = \min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, V_b^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_j^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|} (|P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected} = \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ = |i| E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} = z.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them date back on March 09, 2023.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and

SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. 3271
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The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [76]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. 3273
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In some articles are titled “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022),“(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in 3284
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Ref. [19] by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [90]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [91]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [92]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [93]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [96]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique” in **Ref. [97]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [100]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [103]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [104]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [105]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [106]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [107]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [108]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [119]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)” in **Ref. [120]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [24–44, 46–89, 94, 95, 98, 99, 101, 102, 109–118], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph.

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [121]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google

Scholar and has more than 3230 readers in Scribd. It's titled "Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs" and published by Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United State. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [122]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 4117 readers in Scribd. It's titled "Neutrosophic Duality" and published by Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It's smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what's done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1,2]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions In SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions In SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4-44,46-120]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 3230 and 4117 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [121,122].

References

1. Henry Garrett, "Neutrosophic Co-degree and Neutrosophic Degree alongside Chromatic Numbers in the Setting of Some Classes Related to Neutrosophic Hypergraphs", J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res 1(1) (2022) 06-14.
2. Henry Garrett, "Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes", J Math Techniques Comput Math 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09)
3. Henry Garrett, "Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer's Treatments", J Math Techniques Comput Math 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (<https://www.opastpublishers.com/open-access-articles/some-super-hyper-degrees-and-cosuper-hyper-degrees-on-neutrosophic-super-hyper-graphs-and-super-hyper-graphs-alongside-a.pdf>)
4. Garrett, Henry. "0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph." CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>
5. Garrett, Henry. "0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs." CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>

6. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 3423
3424
3425
3426
7. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 3427
3428
3429
3430
8. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 3431
3432
3433
9. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 3434
3435
3436
3437
3438
3439
10. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 3440
3441
3442
3443
11. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 3444
3445
3446
3447
12. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 3448
3449
3450
3451
13. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3452
3453
3454
14. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 3455
3456
3457
3458
15. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 3459
3460
3461
16. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 3462
3463
3464
17. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3465
3466
3467
3468

18. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 3469
3470
3471
3472
19. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 3473
3474
3475
20. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 3476
3477
3478
3479
3480
21. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 3481
3482
3483
22. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 3484
3485
3486
3487
23. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 3488
3489
3490
3491
24. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 3492
3493
3494
25. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 3495
3496
3497
26. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 3498
3499
3500
27. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 3501
3502
3503
28. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 3504
3505
3506
29. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 3507
3508
3509
30. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 3510
3511
3512

31. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163).
3513
3514
3515
32. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401).
3516
3517
3518
33. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720).
3519
3520
3521
34. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165).
3522
3523
3524
35. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003).
3525
3526
3527
36. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962).
3528
3529
3530
37. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280).
3531
3532
3533
38. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086).
3534
3535
3536
39. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404).
3537
3538
3539
40. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968).
3540
3541
3542
41. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003).
3543
3544
3545
42. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641).
3546
3547
3548
43. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967).
3549
3550
3551
44. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121).
3552
3553
3554
45. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047).
3555
3556
3557

46. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 3558
3559
3560
47. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 3561
3562
3563
48. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 3564
3565
3566
49. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 3567
3568
3569
50. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 3570
3571
3572
51. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 3573
3574
3575
52. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 3576
3577
3578
53. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 3579
3580
3581
54. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 3582
3583
3584
55. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 3585
3586
3587
56. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 3588
3589
3590
57. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 3591
3592
3593
58. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 3594
3595
3596
59. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 3597
3598
3599
60. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 3600
3601
3602

61. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 3603
3604
3605
62. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 3606
3607
3608
63. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 3609
3610
3611
64. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 3612
3613
3614
65. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 3615
3616
3617
66. Henry Garrett, “New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 3618
3619
3620
3621
67. Henry Garrett, “New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 3622
3623
3624
3625
68. Henry Garrett, “New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 3626
3627
3628
3629
69. Henry Garrett, “A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 3630
3631
3632
3633
70. Henry Garrett, “A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 3634
3635
3636
3637
71. Henry Garrett, “A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 3638
3639
3640
3641
72. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 3642
3643
3644
3645
73. Henry Garrett, “Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 3646
3647
3648

74. Henry Garrett, “Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 3649
3650
3651
75. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 3652
3653
3654
76. Henry Garrett, “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 2(1) (2023) 35-47. 3655
3656
3657
3658
77. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 3659
3660
3661
3662
78. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 3663
3664
3665
3666
79. Henry Garrett, “The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing In The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 3667
3668
3669
3670
3671
80. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 3672
3673
3674
3675
3676
81. Henry Garrett, “Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 3677
3678
3679
3680
82. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 3681
3682
3683
83. Henry Garrett, “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 3684
3685
3686
3687
84. Henry Garrett, “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 3688
3689
3690
3691
85. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).). 3692
3693
3694

86. Henry Garrett, “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 3695
3696
3697
3698
3699
3700
87. Henry Garrett, “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 3701
3702
3703
3704
88. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 3705
3706
3707
3708
89. Henry Garrett, “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 3709
3710
3711
3712
90. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 3713
3714
3715
91. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 3716
3717
3718
3719
92. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 3720
3721
3722
3723
93. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 3724
3725
3726
3727
94. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 3728
3729
3730
3731
95. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3732
3733
3734
96. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 3735
3736
3737
97. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 3738
3739
3740
3741

98. Henry Garrett, “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3742
3743
3744
3745
99. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 3746
3747
3748
3749
100. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 3750
3751
3752
3753
101. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 3754
3755
3756
102. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 3757
3758
3759
103. Henry Garrett, “*Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 3760
3761
3762
104. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 3763
3764
3765
105. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 3766
3767
3768
106. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 3769
3770
3771
3772
107. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 3773
3774
3775
108. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 3776
3777
3778
3779
109. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 3780
3781
3782
110. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 3783
3784
3785

111. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 3786
3787
3788
3789
3790
112. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 3791
3792
3793
3794
3795
113. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 3796
3797
3798
114. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 3799
3800
3801
115. Henry Garrett, “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 3802
3803
3804
3805
116. Henry Garrett, “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 3806
3807
3808
3809
117. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 3810
3811
3812
3813
118. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 3814
3815
3816
3817
119. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 3818
3819
3820
120. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 3821
3822
3823
3824
121. Henry Garrett, (2022). “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”, Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United States. ISBN: 979-1-59973-725-6 3825
3826
3827
(<http://fs.unm.edu/BeyondNeutrosophicGraphs.pdf>). 3828
122. Henry Garrett, (2022). “*Neutrosophic Duality*”, Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. ISBN: 978-1-59973-743-0 3829
3830
3831
(<http://fs.unm.edu/NeutrosophicDuality.pdf>). 3832